

CERTIFICATE

OF ACHIVEMENT

this certificate is proudly presented to

NEW INNOVATION IN NATIONAL EDUCATION

JURNALIDA FAOL ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN

Sharafullayeva Shaxlo Qaxramonovna

Etuklik davri inqirozining yosh va jins bilan bog'liqlik jixatlari

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN TAQDIRLANADI

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2022-NOYABR

